

THEORY OF INCREASING VOCABULARY OF STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

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Abstract: This article talks about interactive methods used in English language classes, methods used to increase students' vocabulary. Teaching students to think independently in English classes is an important task before us. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. One of the most important requirements for lessons is to teach students to think independently.

Key words: English language, lesson, interactive methods, student, vocabulary, methods, word, educational system.

During the years of independence, our country faced great changes. This is especially evident in the educational system. Because the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded and mature person. For this, we teachers must use new methods effectively during the lesson. Based on the experience of the developed countries of the world, advanced pedagogical technologies are not only satisfying the interest and needs of young students in learning, but also solving the tasks of training highly qualified specialists.

The state policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a well-rounded person - a citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. In this way, it is to learn about the most basic constitutional rights of a citizen, to show creative ability. - In accordance with the requirements of the Law on Education and the National Program of Personnel Training, we will have to organize classes in a non-traditional way, not in a traditional way. For this, we teachers need to search a lot. Among the world languages, English has a unique position. This international language has become a means of communication on a global scale, and now English is spoken in all regions of the world. It has received the status of a state language in developed countries such as Great Britain, USA, Canada, Australia. Special attention is paid to learning English in our country. Our great-grandfathers knew foreign languages well and made great discoveries in the history of science and culture.

We should teach young people to master foreign languages carefully, being worthy of the spirit of our generations. The use of various games in solving this task gives a positive result. If words are taught through games, students will learn new words quickly, and these words will remain in their memory for a lifetime. Such games can be taught with the whole class or divided into small groups. Let's take a look at some games that teachers can use when teaching new words:

1. Memory game (Memory game) One student says one sentence, another student adds a word or sentence to this sentence:

Student 1: My friend came.

Student 2: My friend and his mother came.

Student 3: My friend and his mother came by train.

Any student who cannot add a word or makes a mistake will leave the game.

2. Word association game. Words related to one class are obtained. For example:

Words related to household appliances.

Student 1: a Sofa.

2nd student: a table.

3rd student: a chair.

4th student: the piano.

Any student who cannot find a word quickly leaves the game.

1. Miming (Miming) This game is designed for high school students, students should know a lot of words, that is, they should have a rich vocabulary. This house may be related to profession. The leader tries to describe the owner of a profession, the rest must find what profession this word refers to, otherwise they can ask questions:

Do you work with children? Do you work in the evening?

2. Game about work tools related to the profession (Guess the tool) The teacher divides the students into pairs. He turns two students face to face and gives them cards with words written on them.

For example: Knife and cook, pen and pupil. These students should not show the writing to each other. Students must describe the word of the tool on the card without saying the name.

Another must find that working tool:

Student 1: It is used for cutting things (bread, vegetables).

Student 2: It is a knife. We use it to prepare meals.

5. Finding words through human sounds (Human sounds) In this house, students learn what sounds people make when they are happy, sad, or sick. Teacher: You are at the concert, at the stage.

Reader: Sings and says I am singing.

Teacher: Someone is here... Student: Whispers some thing and says I am whispering.

Teacher: You hurt your leg.

Reader: Screams and says I am screaming.

At the end of the game, students can find, say and perform similar actions.

6. Suggestion chain game In this game, students make suggestions for spending their free time. To do this, each of them will write down on a piece of paper tonight or tomorrow afternoon, or if not, the weekend, then one of them will start a game, and other students will express their opinions:

Student 1: Let's go to the football match.

Student 2: No, not football. What about going to the concert?

Student 3: We could go to the concert.

Student 4: No, not to the concert.

Why don't we visit the country? The game will continue in this order. All students must share their suggestions. Whoever cannot say the proposal correctly or repeats the previous verb in the sentence will leave the house.

7. Notices and warming practices game The teacher prepares two types of cards. The first type of cards contain phrases and sentences that are spoken in some places. The second type - the cards show the places where these sentences and phrases can be said.

For example:

Student 1: Many students are reading books.

Student 2: In the library.

Student 3: Tickets are sold out.

4th student: Out side the theater.

5th student: Queue for currency exchange.

6th student: Inside a bank.

7. The game used to strengthen the logic (Exaggerate) This method allows students to choose different qualities. For this, the teacher prepares cards with different types of questions: It isn't very interstiny, is it? She is very pretty, isn't she? Did you have a good day? The cards are placed on the table. The teacher calls one of the students, takes one of the cards and orders him to read the question. This student asks another student to answer the question using adjectives.

Student 1: She cooked nice meals, didn't she? Azim?

2nd student: (Azim) Nice? She cooked delicious. Whoever fails to use adjectives appropriately or makes a mistake is considered a loser.

8. Game used to expand the sentences (Expand the sentences) This game is also related to adjectives, several adjectives should be used in the sentences: Teacher: He ate an apple.

Student 1: He ate a red apple.

2nd student: He ate a red big apple.

These types of games help students of all ages to improve their English vocabulary. English teachers can make the conditions of the game easy or complicated, taking into account the age characteristics and knowledge levels of English language learners.

In conclusion, we can make these games easier or harder depending on the level or age of the children. The purpose of these interactive games is different. Through these games, we can concentrate, increase vocabulary, quickness, intelligence, and most importantly, learn the lesson in an interesting way and remember it.

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